

PHILOLOGY

THE PROBLEM OF NATIONAL IDENTITY SEARCHES IN AZERBAIJANI LITERATURE

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Abstract

In the article, the historical novel genre, examples of historical novels in Azerbaijani literature are studied in the context of national identity, national self-awareness and national existence. As the main object of research, historical works written in the years of independence, novels by individual authors, including Eyvaz Zeynalov's "Nadir Shah" novel, which reflects the history of the creation, formation and fall of the Nadir Shah Afshar Empire, are analyzed.

The author of the article examines the events unfolding in the novel from the point of view of Turkic civilizations and the Turkic cultural and historical type. It is emphasized that Nadir Shah created his state at the cost of enormous efforts, but due to backwardness, superstition, lack of education and inexperience in government, the collapse of his empire became inevitable. This led to the subsequent historical tragedies of Azerbaijan, the division and annexation of its historical lands to the territories of individual states.

It is obvious that the Turkic cultural-historical type is not included in the first and subsequent classifications based on the laws and regularities of movement defined by the Russian scientist Nikolay Danilevsky in his work "Russia and Europe", who had the first role in defining cultural-historical types. Historical facts and various types of evidence are listed to prove this. Although the indicated error was eliminated by the authors of the Eurasian concept of Russian history in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, it is noted that there is a need for scientific-theoretical confirmation of the existence of the Turkic cultural-historical type and Turkic civilization as an ideological landmark in the historical conditions of the formation of the Union of Turkic States.

Keywords: historical novel, Nadir Shah Afshar Empire, Eyvaz Zeynalov, Turkic civilizations and Turkic cultural-historical type.

The interest in historical topics in Azerbaijan, particularly the emergence of historical novels during the years of independence, has specific underlying reasons. The root of the approach to historical themes in our literature lies in the persistent assertion that, despite visible efforts, our "academic history has not been correctly written, textbooks have distorted our true history, there is no coherent and unified scientific-historical perspective on the national-ethnic roots of the Azerbaijani people, and the emphasis on presenting our history, ethnography, archaeology, language, folklore, and literature in the broader Turkic and global historical-cultural context and areas remains critically important" – a call that remains highly relevant today.

Given that Eurasianist studies and the problem of the Turkish cultural-historical type in world cultures and civilizations are now part of our research interests, we consider it essential in our literature, especially during the post-Soviet period of independence, to promote and present to ourselves and others: national self-awareness, national identity, our national statehood history, the determination of independent Azerbaijan's place and role in the broader Turkic historical-cultural arena, and our existence as a political and economic force in the region, the Turkish States Union, and the world – emphasizing our status as possessors of a great history and culture, free thought, self-confidence, and wholeness.

In this context, we would like to focus specifically on Eyvaz Zeynalov's novel "Nadir Shah", (Zeynalov, 2024, 568 p.) as it evokes diverse intellectual associations.

The persistent interest in the image of Nadir Shah, dubbed "The last Conqueror of the East", is particularly evident in our literary works. Naturally, Nariman Narimanov's drama "Nadir Shah" stands out first in this context. After Huseynbala Miralamov's "The Last Conqueror" and Yunus Oguz's "Nadir Shah" novels were published in the post-Soviet period, Professor Lawrence Lockhart's monograph "Nadir Shah" from Cambridge University, and in parallel, British orientalist Michael Axworthy's "The Sword of Persia: Nadir Shah. From Tribal Warrior to Conquering Tyrant" (published in Azerbaijani in 2018) emerged. The previously translated monograph "Nadir Shah" by Iranian historian Mohammad Hossein Qoddusi was a valuable source for our writers. The publication of E. Zeynalov's extensive "Nadir Shah" novel in 2024, followed by the translation of Mirza Mehdi Khan Astarabadi's "History of Nadir: the Conqueror of the World" by researcher-scholar and renowned translator Ibrahim Guliyev, demonstrates the continued relevance of the topic. It is worth noting that Yunus Oguz's novel has already been published in Turkish and English, while Huseynbala Miralamov's novel is available in English. According to the author, E. Zeynalov's novel is also being prepared for publication in Turkish and German.

Zeynalov is the latest author to approach the historical novel genre and the history of the creation, expansion, and decline of the empire of the Azerbaijani Turk Nadir Shah. Naturally, he has extensively utilized the sources listed in his bibliography. Simultaneously, through the power of his artistic imagination and extensive, productive writing experience, he has managed to

present his original plot and interpretation. Specifically mentioning Lockhart's book, we would emphasize that its version translated by our renowned writer Nariman Abdulrahmanli is not only a comprehensive scientific-historical-chronological source but also a publication presented in a highly artistic, vivid, and readable language. The message conveyed in the first chapter of Lockhart's work confirms his intention as a researcher and the invaluable nature of this precisely translated work for our historiography. The "Final Notes" of the English scholar, who conducted extensive research, indicate that examining and presenting materials from archives in Tehran, Moscow, St.Petersburg, Istanbul, Vienna, Paris, and other cities regarding the contradictory period of the Safavid and Nadir Shah Afshar empires remains a primary task of our most recent historiography. The significance of Lockhart's research, observations, and conclusions lies in exposing the fundamental reasons for the decline of the magnificent Safavid and Afshar empires created by Azerbaijani Turks – a perspective we urgently need to revisit. It appears that the author does not remain impartial towards Nadir Shah's heroism and approaches it with admiration: *"Rising from shepherding to kingship should be considered a significant achievement, but Nadir's even greater heroism was that he not only liberated the Safavid Empire, which had been torn apart by powerful enemies, but also elevated the country from its lowest level to the most influential state in Asia"* (Zeynalov, 2024, p.5).

In the depiction by Mirza Mehdi Khan Astarabadi, who serves as Nadir Shah's chronicler, a powerful conqueror's image is vividly portrayed: *"This divine force created Nadir, the world conqueror, as a magnificent protector of the homeland like [Great] Alexander, a renowned [Warlord] victorious on the battlefield, or a manifestation of divine power laboring [to restore] a fallen name. He is a courageous conqueror who adorns the royal seal, shines like a star in world dominion, is worthy of the royal throne that embellishes the world, and possesses the power to triumph over enemies... The earth has drawn its shield over its head in fear of his arrow"* (Zeynalov, 2024, p.15).

This novel, covering events of the 18th century – a new era, presents a challenging and thought-provoking narrative for Azerbaijani Turks who consider the Safavid and Nadir Shah Afshar empires a significant stage of their historical legacy. The topic of Nadir Shah is historically closer to our time, making materials from local and foreign archives and books written by foreigners accessible to researchers and readers.

The novel's notable characteristics include the preservation of historical-chronological sequence, emphasis on key historical facts throughout the narrative, clear and convincing descriptions, the ability to artistically clothe historical facts, vivid portrayal of human characters and the epoch. It explores Nadir Shah Afshar Empire's relations with Russian and Ottoman states, Nadir Shah's confrontations with mountaineers and Dagestani peoples, complex religious issues for the Islamic world, and provides a comprehensive explanation of the reforms of Nadir Shah, particularly regarding inter-sectarian contradictions – a primary source of

discord between the two major Muslim empires of the East.

The work does not shy away from an abundance of battle scenes consistent with the genre, a successful depiction of the military and warrior spirit created by Nadir Shah as a commander, and an attempt to create an image of a reformist ruler ensuring the country's military and economic might. Simultaneously, the novel highlights the penetration into the inner world and thoughts of humans caught in the whirlpool of death, torture, and other inhumane factors.

The author successfully creates a comprehensive understanding of Nadir, who was raised in a simple family, strengthened by the warrior spirit in accordance with the demands of his environment and time, and who rose from an army commander to the shah's advisor and ultimately to the shah's position. Following the tradition of medieval literature, the commander and ruler Nadir Shah is portrayed as a fearless, indefatigable, resolute tactical and strategic leader:

"Nadir was not intimidated by the enemy's numerical superiority. In battle, he favored swift cavalry attacks. His cavalymen were skilled in firing while making rapid attacks and hitting targets accurately. Their horses were extremely fast. His cavalry was famous throughout Asia. They had an impressive appearance. They wore four-cornered leather caps, and were armed with rifles, axes, swords, and shields. They would not attack unless they heard Nadir's order, and when they did attack, they were unstoppable. He had personally trained them on the battlefields" (Zeynalov, 2024, pp. 264-265).

The depiction under the chapter titled "Translation of Holy Scriptures" in the second part of the novel elucidates that Nadir Shah's approach to religious reforms and his attitude toward religion were not guided by blind faith. During the debates, Nadir Shah declares his intent: *"My first goal is to eliminate the sectarian differences that divide the Turks"* (Zeynalov, 2024, p. 443).

This brief analysis and our engagement with the text enables us to evaluate the era and events described within the context of the New Era stage of world history. The 18th century was a period of bourgeois revolutions, classicism, and Enlightenment in Europe. The final decades of the century are characterized by the flourishing of sentimentalism and romanticism in Europe and Russia. In other words, philosophical and literary thought focused on the image of the simple human, the inner world of individuals, and the struggles of freedom-loving fighters. By this time, the protagonist of the emerging Masonic movement in Europe was the hardworking, creative human.

In the near future, 18th-century Russia, which would dominate the Caucasus, surrounding territories, historical Azerbaijani lands, Crimea, and Black and Baltic Sea ports, was experiencing technological revival and pursuing the path of enlightenment, sometimes following and sometimes even overtaking Europe. As the novel reveals, a completely different socio-political and cultural-spiritual environment existed in the Nadir Shah Empire and the Ottoman Empire at that time. Indeed, apart from rare attempts such as Nadir

Shah's desires to create a naval fleet, conduct improvement works, and collect taxes, it was difficult to speak of any technical progress, spread of enlightened ideas, or establishment of a progressive education system in the country.

So, although Nadir Shah was called a conqueror, the era of conquerors had already passed in history. Subsequent and even contemporary history demonstrated that achieving economic and cultural progress and political influence through war, force, oppression, and cruelty is challenging. This was repeatedly proven by the political fate of Napoleon, another conqueror from a simple background who is often compared with Nadir Shah. Even Nadir Shah's attempts to subjugate Caucasian peoples – the mountaineers – would be sufficient to precipitate the collapse of his powerful but short-lived empire. In the 19th-20th centuries, Russia has repeated the same mistake: according to estimates, it lost more than 30 million officers and soldiers in the conquest of the Caucasus.

Mammadh Said Ordubadi's "Sword and Pen", a novel with profound ideas and national-historical coloration, provided direction for the future of the historical novel genre and thematic explorations in our literature. Among the artistic works we loved most since childhood are Ismayil Shikhli's "Tameless Kura River", Farman Karimzadeh's "The Khudafarin Bridge", Alisa Nijat's "Qizilbashs", Aziza Jafarzadeh's "Baku 1501" and others. It is not coincidental that these works have been republished multiple times during the years of independence. During the independence years, especially in the last two decades, there emerged a necessity both to comprehend the genuine truths related to our national history and to communicate them to ourselves and others. Because it has become evident that the perceptions formed during the Soviet era about general Turkic and Azerbaijani history were incorrect, with events being distorted and presented in line with ideological agendas over time. Fortunately, we were in a position to rely on the magnificent historical essays of Abbasgulu Agha Bakikhanov, such as "Gulistani-Iram", which reflected our true history before the Russian invasion in 1805, 1813, and 1828. Unfortunately, despite this valuable historical source being deemed as important for Russian historiography as Nikolai Karamzin's twelve-volume "History of the Russian State" and being recommended for review and publication by the Russian Academy of Sciences and the Ministry of Education, it was only printed at the author's own expense due to the lack of financial resources. Furthermore, in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, among the intellectuals who contributed to the development of Turkism and national self-awareness in the Russian and Turkish socio-political, scientific, and philosophical environments, were prominent figures such as Ahmad Bey Aghayev and Ali Bey Huseynzade. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, established in the East, became the first democratic republic in the region, realizing the formation of our people's long-standing statehood within the framework of national self-awareness, under the banners of Turkism, Islamism, and modernity (Europeanization), in response to the demands of the time. By the verdict of history, Azerbaijan, a people with a rich history, culture, and ancient statehood experience, located at the

crossroads of Europe and Asia, where the Silk Road and trade routes intersect, endured a long and painful yet magnificent and bitter journey of statehood. Despite these challenges, the Azerbaijani people were able to establish a civil state that responded to the modern challenges of the era, achieving significant accomplishments in a short period of almost two years. In our opinion, in the current socio-political context, the thesis of Ahmed Agaoglu, "As for us, we could not even teach our language to strangers, let alone to the nomads; we have no national craft except backward agriculture, and the scope of our intellect and mind is limited... We cannot avoid the necessity of adopting the victorious (European – T.J.) culture. This truth, however bitter, must be acknowledged and acted upon accordingly" (Ağaoglu, 2006, p. 35), proved to be of great value.

By liberating Baku, which had become the center of the economic interests of world imperialism, Tsarist and later Soviet Russia, we not only fought a fierce war with the Armenians who had been settled on our fertile lands as a result of the Russo-Iranian and Russo-Ottoman Wars, but also managed to restore our historical memory and deepen our understanding of national identity. Despite the Soviet occupation, this national awakening and consciousness continued to yield results in the 1920s and 1930s. The First Turkological Congress, held in Baku in 1926, raised the claims of Azerbaijan's legacy to the general Turkic history of statehood and culture, as well as its vast historical and cultural area. Azerbaijan's political and literary diaspora fulfilled its mission in this regard until the end. The ideological and thematic profundity of our magnificent medieval epic "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" ("The Book of Dada Gorgud"), the statehood traditions of the Oghuz Turks meticulously portrayed within its narrative, their nuanced experiences in confronting both internal and external adversaries, as well as the scholarly comparisons drawn by Russian and European Orientalists with seminal epics such as the "Tale of Igor's Host", the "Song of Roland", and the "Nibelungenlied", have provoked profound scholarly interest and intellectual discourse. The epic was translated into foreign languages (by figures such as Friedrich von Dittes, Vasili Vladimirovich Bartold, etc.). The Oghuz-Turkic epic, with its ideological and thematic depth, literary-artistic richness, challenges, originality, and poetics, embraced all of these aforementioned works.

Since the era of Mirza Fatali Akhundov, the idea of Europeanization and the recognition of the dark chapters in our history led to the transition to the Latin script. The works of figures like Huseyn Javid, Almas Ildirim, Mahammad Hadi, Ahmad Javad, Mikayil Mushfig, and others, particularly H. Javid's historical dramas ("The Prophet", "Siyavush", "Tyrant Timur", "Khayyam") urged the people to understand their historical past and never forget their "blood memory". Thirdly, during the period of mass repression and deportation of peoples, which intensified in the mid-1930s and continued sharply until Stalin's death, the ideological clichés formed during this time, and the distorted presentation of our great historical past in encyclopedic publications, school textbooks, and academic works until the collapse of the Soviet government and the communist regime, failed to erase the concepts of

“national self-awareness” and “historical memory”. Late academic Bekir Nabiye, in his foreword to H. Miralamov’s *“The Last Conqueror”*, compares the entries on Nadir Shah and Napoleon Bonaparte in the *Azerbaijan Soviet Encyclopedia* and expresses astonishment at the distorted and diminutive portrayal of the Azerbaijani ruler and commander in comparison to the French general.

In the 1960s, efforts to expand the functionality of the Azerbaijani language and restore national customs and traditions (led by figures such as Mirza Ibrahimov, Shikhali Gurbanov, and others), as well as the formation of the “sixties” generation (including Isa Huseynov, Chingiz Huseynov, Anar, Akram Aylisli, and others) who brought national spirit and self-awareness into literature, marked a significant cultural shift. In subsequent years, under the National Leader Heydar Aliyev, the Azerbaijani language was officially recognized as the state language in the Republic’s Constitution, further solidifying the calls for national self-awareness. This movement gained even more momentum in the poetry of the 1970s and 1980s (with poets like Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh, Mammad Araz, and others), and, particularly in the late 1980s, amid unfounded territorial claims over Karabakh, there was a revival of the people’s historical memory and fighting spirit. The press and journalism, including Sabir Rustamkhanli’s “The Book of Life”, the “Azerbaijan” newspaper restored under his initiative, and other works, contributed to this national awakening and freedom movement. These efforts ultimately led to the realization of the idea of restoring our independence and statehood. Despite all the prohibitions and the fervor of Soviet propaganda, generations that had witnessed more recent historical events – especially representatives of our literature – were able to keep historical issues in the public discourse through their work aimed at restoring national and “blood” memory. Key examples of this include Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh’s “Gulistan” poem, Yusuf Samadoglu’s “The Day of the Killing”, Sabir Rustamkhanli’s poem called “Blood Memory” and many other works that played a crucial role in the national struggle.

The calamities inflicted upon our nation between 1989 and 1994, including the forced displacement of nearly one million compatriots from their ancestral lands with the support of neighboring states, subjected them to decades of exile. This exile sought to impose not only physical dislocation but also the erasure of land, national dignity, patriotic consciousness, and most importantly, historical memory. These challenges posed a profound responsibility for our literature, press, and social and humanities disciplines: to comprehend and assess the prevailing historical conditions, foster national identity and Azerbaijani studies, and cultivate a sense of Azerbaijani patriotism.

In the challenging post-First Karabakh War period, questions surrounding the causes of our defeat and losses also served as a catalyst for intellectual inquiry and artistic exploration. It is no coincidence that historical novels with postmodernist tendencies and artistic-aesthetic perspectives emerged during this time. Works such as Sabir Rustamkhanli’s “Göy Tanrı” (“Tengri”), Kamal Abdulla’s “Yarımçıq Əlyazma” (The Incomplete Manuscript), and Anar’s “Ağ Qoç, Qara Qoç”

(“The White Ram, The Black Ram”), among others, captivated readers through their combination of mythopoetic elements, folklore motifs, and their grounding in historical events. These novels provided a lens through which the events depicted were interpreted in light of the authors’ contemporary challenges and societal demands.

The historical novels of these authors, therefore, did not merely reflect the epochs they described; rather, they resonated with the spirit and exigencies of the authors’ own time.

In the 2020 Patriotic War, referred to as the Second Karabakh War, Azerbaijan succeeded in reclaiming its territories and asserting its rightful claims through its strength while garnering substantial international support.

In our view, Azerbaijani literature became one of the standard-bearers of this historic struggle. In this context, it is worth highlighting three historical novels that, despite differing in themes and narrative styles, intersect in their treatment of significant historical events. Sabir Rustamkhanli’s “Ölüm zirvəsi” (“The Peak of Death”) vividly portrays the heroic resistance of Javad Khan, the ruler of the Ganja Khanate, along with his family and defenders of the city-fortress, who fought to their last breath against the overwhelming forces of Russian General Sisianov, deprived of any external support. Elchin’s “Baş” (“The Head”) focuses on the story of the same Russian general, narrating the symbolic tale of his beheaded remains at the gates of another city-fortress, Baku. In contrast, Elchin Huseynbeyli’s “Yenə iki od arasında” (“Once again between two fires”), inspired by Yusif Vazir Chamanzaminli’s “İki od arasında” (“Between two fires”), explores similar themes with distinct narrative and stylistic approaches. Additionally, Elchin Huseynbeyli’s “Karabakh Tales” captures the true essence of our nation’s search for peace during the occupation of our territories.

These works collectively reflect the resilience, sacrifice, and historical consciousness of our people, contributing to the preservation and promotion of national identity through literature.

While scrutinizing established theories regarding world cultural and civilizational histories, we pause to emphasize the marginalization of the Turkic cultural-historical archetype. We critically examine the perspectives of prominent scholars who have historically diminished Turkic contributions. Russian scholar Nikolay Danilevsky’s assertion in his 1869 work “Russia and Europe” that these tribes remained at the “ethnographic material level”, having either not participated in historical processes or only risen to the level of destructive historical elements, demands scholarly reappraisal. Similarly, we wonder the dismissive approaches of German philosopher Oswald Spengler, who largely passed over Turkic cultural histories in silence in his work “The Decline of Europe” (Spengler O., https://antilogicalism.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/decline_of_the_west.pdf) and British historian Arnold Toynbee, who categorized Turkic civilizations as “frozen” and characterized Turks as mere destroyers of civilizations (Toynbee A. Study of History

chive.org/de-tails/in.ernet.dli.2015.460039/page/n1/mode/2up) or labeled them with ambiguous terms like “Ottoman” or “nomadic”.

L.Lockhart's perspectives on the decline and fall of Nader's dynasty and the preceding Safavid dynasty compel us to approach the matter from an alternative analytical prism. The primary cause of Nadir Shah's downfall is attributed to a characteristic moral collapse typical of monarchs (as exemplified in E.Zeynalov's novel “Nader Shah”: the merciless flogging of Nadir's beloved brother Ibrahim before his young son's eyes, thereby fostering future hatred and creating conditions for vengeance in the potential future commander Aligulu Khan; the inexplicable blinding of his primary heir, the crown prince and great commander Rzagulu, thus losing his principal successor; the unceasing brutality including constructing Timur-style pyramids of heads in the 18th century, violence against women, and persistent acts of cruelty – all of which constituted the path to moral deterioration and ultimate collapse).

The English scholar's reflections on the Safavids prompt us to revisit the narratives of Azerbaijani authors. *“Heirs to the throne, sequestered in their harems and isolated from the world, consequently deprived of comprehensive education... could not learn the art of warfare or governance while confined within harem walls. Moreover, they frequently fell under the influence of self-interested eunuchs. Thus, upon the time of succession, it would become apparent that the heir was entirely unprepared to fulfill royal responsibilities, thereby being compelled to rely entirely on eunuchs and nobles. One of the fundamental causes of the Safavid dynasty's decline was their indifferent attitude towards the military, resulting in a gradual reduction of troops and diminishing combat effectiveness”* (Lokkart, 2018, p. 6). Similar negative descriptions and perspectives regarding the Safavids are found in the diaries of Western European envoys, travelers, and merchants, including Jean Chardin, Jean-Baptiste Tavernier, Engelbert Kaempfer, Adam Olearius, Jan Streys, Pietro Della Valle, and others (Süleymanov, 2021).

A peculiar parallel arises in E.Zeynalov's novel “Nadir Shah”, set against the backdrop of the Sunni-Shi'a conflict that threatened Islamic unity. Nadir Shah's appeals to the Ottoman Sultan-Caliph and the wars waged for this purpose seem futile in the face of his assassination. Following his death, his entire lineage, even pregnant women in his harem, were massacred. Meanwhile, within the Ottoman and Persian realms, fraternal rivalries saw siblings blinded or beheaded, with domes of skulls symbolizing power struggles. All this unfolded in the East during an era in Europe that saw the emergence of Enlightenment thinkers like Voltaire, Rousseau, Diderot, Kant, La Fontaine, and Goethe, who championed human freedom and dignity.

Nadir Shah, the ruler of the Afsharid Empire, punished his eldest son and heir, Rzagulu, with medieval severity reminiscent of the Inquisition's harshest practices, though this decision came after extensive deliberations with his council of viziers. One might ponder: could this state, which emerged from the ruins of the Safavid Empire and positioned itself as an empire of

Azerbaijani Turks, not have been sustained despite the formidable pressures exerted by Russian, Ottoman, and European powers? Nadir Shah, a man of humble origins lacking formal education and political pedigree, nonetheless managed to reclaim Safavid territories from the Ottomans, expel Russia from the Caucasus, and initiate ambitious maritime strategies, including establishing a nascent navy on the Caspian and attempting to capture Astrakhan. Remarkably, he accomplished these extraordinary feats during the period of heightened imperial expansion characterized by Peter the Great and his successors in Russia.

Nadir Shah's religious reforms and reflections on Islam's societal role, though imperfect, invite comparison to the Protestant Reformation in Christianity. However, his lack of an intellectual and literary milieu, with philosophers, poets, and influential religious figures absent from his court, had significant consequences. The character of the mollabashi in Zeynalov's novel caricatures a land dominated by ignorance, illiteracy, and oppression. Contrast this with Western scholars such as Adam Olearius, George Makdisi, Jean-Baptiste Tavernier, and Engelbert Kaempfer, who highlighted education and cultural progress as key factors during the Safavid Empire's zenith (Ahmad A.; <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/2320677>). As Asgar Ahmed's extensive references to foreign and local authors suggest, the Safavid Empire's success owed much to its education system, which encompassed all social strata, including orphans. Alongside court schools providing religious, secular, and military training for princes and nobles, even women and girls in the harem received comprehensive education, a detail noted by foreign envoys and travelers. However, the abolition of the lalelik (mentorship) institution during Shah Abbas's reign, delegating education to eunuchs, left its mark. Similar trends in the Ottoman Empire, such as the reliance on janissaries, eunuchs, and foreign women with no ethnic allegiance, stifled passionarity in the long-lived Turkish empire.

The example of Nadir Shah's Afsharid model demonstrates that human development, shaped by individual upbringing and environment, holds as much historical significance as technological advancements. After all, it is humans who program technology and artificial intelligence, directing them toward the well-being of their people, country, and humanity at large.

The assassination of Nadir Shah and the sudden, ruthless, and disgraceful collapse of the empire he built had a profoundly tragic impact on Azerbaijan's subsequent history. The Qajars, ethnically Azerbaijani Turks, failed to consolidate the fragmented territories of the empire into a cohesive political and military force capable of resisting Russia. Unfortunately, the Russo-Persian wars of the 19th century, followed by the Second World War, thwarted the unification of our historic lands, even when the opportunity for full integration arose. The efforts of our infamous neighbors ensured that these territories remained divided, preventing their union within a single state.

We conclude our discourse with L.N. Gumilev's words from “Ancient Rus and the Great Steppe” (Гумилев, 2000, p. 704): *“Within each of us resides a genetic memory that remains imperceptible in daily life*

yet periodically emerges from the subconscious". Our purpose is not to look backward, but forward—towards reinforcing the Azerbaijani individual's commitment and service to the Homeland and land, and expanding our nation's and state's positive image across broader cultural-historical domains, drawing upon our accumulated scholarly and artistic heritage, state-building experience, and conceptualizations of religious and national identity. In this context, we consider it essential to conduct comprehensive analyses of numerous historical-themed works and extensive novels written during the years of independence, examining them within the frameworks of historical existence, national identity, and the epoch's national ideological quests. Furthermore, we advocate for their purposeful presentation across diverse readership demographics, educational curricula, national-ideological, strategic research, and promotional platforms.

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